

Explanations for Trustworthy AI in Critical Infrastructure: A Case from Wastewater Treatment in Norway

Position paper for the CHI 2025 workshop HCXAI

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Artificial intelligence applications in critical infrastructure poses requirements for explainability and interpretability, something that is also accentuated in recent European legislation on AI. In this position paper, we provide a glimpse into an ongoing project on AI development and implementation to improve highly instrumented wastewater treatment processes, with demands for explainability and interpretability to satisfy quality demands and requirements for trustworthy AI. Taking a starting point in previous HCXAI and XAI contributions, we discuss three takeaways from the case concerning (a) the benefit of targeted explanations, (b) the need for explanations to drive user action, and the implications of inaccurate explanations. In conclusion, we reflect on the role of explanations in assessments and audits of AI-applications critical infrastructure.

CCS CONCEPTS • **Human-centered computing** → **Human computer interaction (HCI)**

Additional Keywords and Phrases: Human-centred explainable AI, trustworthy AI, critical infrastructure

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1 INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) holds promise for substantial improvements to critical infrastructure, such as that of transportation and supply of water or energy. Expected cross-sector benefits include, e.g., increased efficiency, performance improvements, and predictive analysis [1,17]. Responsible uptake of AI in critical infrastructure, however, requires that it is developed and implemented in adherence to principles of trustworthy AI [5,13] where the accuracy and robustness of AI, as well as its explainability and interpretability are key. The importance of explainability and interpretability is accentuated in recent European legislation on AI. As such, human-centred explainable AI (HCXAI) is becoming a legally required aspect of assessments and audits of AI systems in critical infrastructure.

In this position paper, we share experiences from an ongoing case of developing AI applications for a specific critical infrastructure, that of wastewater treatment, and use these as background on which to reflect on implications for HCXAI in assessments and audits for this purpose, specifically with regards to model performance. The case thereby expands on topics of previous studies presented to at previous HCXAI workshops, particularly Schneider et al.'s [14] discussion of targeted explanations in safety-critical domains and Mansi and Riedl's [12] framework for AI explanations and user action. It also relates to Cabitza et al.'s [4] study on the potentially detrimental effects of inaccurate explanations presented at the conference Explainable AI (XAI) 2024.

In the remainder of the paper, we first provide an overview of our specific case. We then allow previous HCXAI and XAI studies to guide our discussions of key takeaways from the case. Specifically, we discuss the benefit of targeted explanations, the need for explanations to drive user action, and the implications of inaccurate explanations, before reflecting on the role of explanations in assessments and audits of AI-applications in critical infrastructure, specifically in the light of the evolving landscape of AI regulation.

2 THE CASE: EXPLANATIONS FOR TRUSTWORTHY AI IN WASTEWATER TREATMENT

The case of our position paper is the development of AI-applications to improve efficiency and quality of wastewater treatment at a Norwegian wastewater treatment facility, Veas (<https://veas.nu/>). Wastewater treatment is part of the critical infrastructure of any urban settlement. As cities grow, the volume of wastewater from households, commercial and government institutions and industry increases to a point where the underwater environment is at risk [16]. To mitigate negative environmental impact, wastewater treatment has advanced substantially of the past decades, with complex processing to remove garbage, organic matter, and nutrients [10]. Current wastewater processing is highly instrumented with advanced control systems, paving the road for improvements through AI [11].

At Veas, time series data from the control system is made available for the training of AI models to make predictions on the wastewater treatment process. AI model development and assessment is conducted as part of the European research and innovation action FAITH (<https://faith-ec-project.eu/>), specifically addressing human-centred trustworthy AI.

Currently, Veas AI models are being developed for the wastewater treatment phase concerning removal of nitrate, a significant wastewater nutrient leading to increase in algae growth and destabilization of marine ecosystems. By predicting nitrate levels in outflowing wastewater, given relevant process parameters, the aim is to substantially increase the efficiency and effectiveness of nitrate removal [2]. However, AI models for this purpose need to account for the substantial variation in the wastewater treatment process due to seasonal variation and weather conditions. For example, heavy rainfall or low water temperatures significantly impacts wastewater treatment effectiveness. The accuracy of model predictions may, hence, vary substantially over different time periods [9].

For Veas stakeholders, the decision to make use of AI applications in wastewater treatment requires that the underlying AI models are sufficiently accurate and robust. Here, robustness concerns accuracy when a particular perturbation is applied [3]. Given the substantial variability in model accuracy across time periods, with perturbations driven by season or weather, general assessments of model accuracy and robustness is not sufficient. Rather assessments of accuracy of specific predictions should be available to process engineers and operators at runtime, to assess the need for human action at times of insufficient accuracy. Furthermore, prediction accuracy and robustness needs to be assessed as part of routine reviews and audits required as per general quality system requirements, e.g., in ISO 9001 [7].

In consequence, for stakeholders at Veas, intuitive and accessible runtime measures of accuracy and robustness will be highly important. And, in cases of inadequate accuracy or robustness, explanations of the basis for model predictions are

required. This may in particular be relevant for longer time periods where accuracy is low, to identify factors that might impact robustness and, thereby, propose mitigating actions.

Explanations for AI model performance is also important to satisfy future possible requirements related to recent AI legislation in Europe. Norway, as part of the Europe Economic Area, is currently implementing the European AI Act [6]. The legislation entered into force in 2024 and will have full applicability in 2026. It imposes substantial requirements on AI for purposes classified as high-risk – such as safety components of critical infrastructure [ibid., annex III]. To comply with the requirements of legislation, high-risk AI systems need to be transparent, with needed traceability and explainability, so as to enable appropriate use [ibid., article 13] with adequate levels of accuracy and robustness [ibid., article 15]. Furthermore, management of risk associated with the AI system is a cornerstone of the AI Act, where AI system owners are required to conduct AI risk management continuously throughout the entire life-cycle of high-risk AI systems [ibid., article 9].

Following this brief presentation of the case, we now discuss three key takeaways with the basis in previous papers on HCXAI and XAI and make concluding reflections with regards to one of the main workshop topics.

3 TAKEAWAY 1: THE BENEFIT OF TARGETED EXPLANATIONS

The success of AI-applications to improve efficiency and effectiveness in critical infrastructure, such as that of wastewater treatment, requires explanations that target stakeholders and users. As argued by Schneider et al. [14] in a 2024 HCXAI paper, AI-powered automation may widen the gap between operator accountability and control. When this happens, the explainability and interpretability of AI-based systems may be instrumental to provide stakeholders with needed information and visibility to negotiate the alignment of accountability and control. For this purpose, explanations and access to metrics needs to be tailored to the specific needs of the stakeholders.

This insight is highly relevant for our case of AI-applications for wastewater treatment. The introduction of AI for process control potentially may challenge accountability and control unless information and explanations needed for user and stakeholders, such as process engineers and operators, fit their needs. The lack of relevant information and explanations would reduce the trustworthiness of the AI-applications and hamper their uptake. Acknowledging the importance of targeted explanations, the design and development of the interface will follow the principles of human-centred AI [15], where a key components are substantial stakeholder involvement throughout the process and an iterative approach to AI development and implementation.

4 TAKEAWAY 2: THE NEED FOR EXPLANATIONS TO DRIVE USER ACTION

Explanations of AI can be instrumental to drive needed user action. Mansie and Riedl [12] addressed this in a paper presented at HCXAI 2023 and provided a framework connecting AI explanations and corresponding relevant user actions. The framework was motivated by a need in the XAI community to gain such an overview, and it is also useful as a map to guide project-specific considerations and expectations with regards to relevant XAI interactions.

The mapping of Mansie and Riedl is helpful for our purposes in the development of AI-models for critical infrastructure. In a domain such as wastewater treatment, model performance is highly important, and corresponding considerations for users may entail judgements of consistency or performance and decisions on continued usage or the need for mitigating action. For explanations concerning model performance, Mansie and Riedl notes that users may, e.g., require more or different information or request an audit. In our case, the human-centred process will allow for identifying needs for information and explanation during AI model and application development. Specifically, we aim to use dedicated stakeholder evaluation workshops throughout the development process for this purpose. This will help provide needed

runtime provision of information and explanations of relevance to assessing and understanding model accuracy and robustness, so as to take needed mitigating action, for example in the form of human intervention or AI model changes to address robustness issues for time periods. Furthermore, in line with implications from the work of Mansie and Riedl, we will during evaluations focus on user actions enabled by provided information and explanations.

5 TAKEAWAY 3: THE IMPLICATIONS OF INACCURATE EXPLANATIONS

While it is well established that explanations may enhance users' ability to make adequate use of AI, Cabitza and colleagues [4] in a paper presented at XAI 2024 note that for explanations to have this effect they need to enable users to form an adequate understanding of eventual issues and possible means of mitigation. In situations of inadequate or even misleading explanations, users may be induced to take erroneous mitigation actions – or fail to take needed action. Cabitza and colleagues refers to this as an explainability paradox, and make specific note of situations where misleading explanations may lead uses to disregard valid AI system advice in decision making processes.

The explainability paradox may be a valuable phenomenon to consider with regards to our use case on AI models to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of wastewater treatment. As note, it is key for stakeholders to assess the prediction accuracy during operations and both prediction accuracy and robustness during routine reviews and audits, where simple reviews could be conducted as often as on a daily basis. To maintain AI trustworthiness, it will be highly important to adequately address deviations in accuracy or robustness. To do this, Veas process engineers and operators will have access to information on AI prediction accuracy as well as explanations for predictions. One relevant form of explanations may be based on identifying time periods with similar characteristics and model performance issues to the current time period, which in turn may be used to identify characteristics associated with the given issue. However, following the explainability paradox, it will be necessary to ensure that provided explanations motivate users to make adequate decisions on whether or not to disregard AI model predictions. Following the lead of Cabitza and colleagues this could, for example, be set up as experimental user studies.

6 CONCLUDING REFLECTIONS: EXPLANATIONS IN ASSESSMENTS AND AUDITS OF AI-APPLICATIONS CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

We have presented a case of AI development for improving efficiency and effectiveness in wastewater treatment. To achieve this objective, and comply with requirements for trustworthy AI [5,13], the AI application needs to be sufficiently accurate and robust to provide adequate control. It further needs to provide information and explanations that allow process engineers and operators insight into the basis for its output, both as a source of validation or to drive identification of issues and mitigation needs.

Being critical infrastructure, wastewater treatment at Veas already is subject to extensive quality management processes, following international standards for quality management [7] and management of environmental impact [8]. As part of their quality system, process operators and engineers engage in routine reviews and audits of management of the wastewater treatment processes and related support systems. Consequently, any implementation of AI support in the wastewater treatment process will need to be included in adequate corresponding quality management processes and relevant reviews and audits.

For this purpose, information and explanations on AI model performance and prediction accuracy and robustness will be highly important input to quality management in general and routine reviews and audits in particular. Information on AI prediction accuracy and robustness will be a key point of assessment for AI models applied for wastewater treatment process control. Furthermore, explanations of model predictions may be instrumental in part to decide (a) whether and

when human intervention is needed as part of a human-in-the-loop response procedure and (b) whether and how any mitigation measures are needed to improve the AI model or its interface to the users.

The evolving regulatory landscape adds to the relevance of information and explanations on AI predictions. Europe is a leading region in terms of AI regulation and the ongoing implementation of the AI Act entails both promise and challenges. For AI system providers and owners, a key initial need will be to clearly characterize any specific AI application in terms of its risk level. For applications characterized as high risk – such as safety components in the management and operation of critical infrastructure – there will be substantial requests for information and explanations of AI model as input to required AI risk management processes. The AI Act will be fully implemented in 2026. To prepare for this, considerations of how to design and develop AI applications to enable needed information and explanations should have high priority.

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